

Netherlands Institute for Space Research

Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document for Sentinel-5 Precursor: TROPOMI CH4 Random Forest Cloud Filter

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1 Introduction

1.1 Identification

This document describes the novel approach of employing a RFC for cloud clearing in the operational TROPOMI XCH₄ product. With the goal of achieving a product accuracy of <1%, robust cloud filtering is essential. Historically, operational XCH₄ data processing relied on SUOMI-National Polar-orbiting Partnership (SUOMI-NPP) VIIRS cloud observations. However, with SUOMI-NPP nearing the end of its operational tenure and experiencing malfunctions in 2022 and 2023, an alternative approach was necessitated. In this investigation, we introduce a machine learning-driven cloud-clearing strategy anchored on the RFC framework. The RFC is trained on co-located TROPOMI and SUOMI-NPP VIIRS datasets to mirror VIIRS-like cloud clearing. Post-training, cloud masking necessitates solely TROPOMI data, thus ensuring operational autonomy from SUOMI-NPP.

1.2 Purpose and objectives

This document outlines the theoretical framework of the RFC cloud clearing approach for refining TROPOMI CH₄ data. It describes the training process, compares the accuracy of predictions with VIIRS-based methods, and validates the data against ground-based TCCON stations to ensure mission requirements are met. Additionally, it highlights the provision of three trained RFCs for cloud fractions of 0.1, 0.02, and 0.001. A brief comparison with GOSAT-2 is provided to analyze global coverage and the biases in the measurements.

1.3 Document overview

The document is structured as follows. After the introduction, Section 2 provides a list of abbreviations used in this document, followed by references in Section 3. Section 4 provides a concise overview of the TROPOMI CH₄, CO, and VIIRS data products, emphasizing their significance in ensuring data quality for TROPOMI CH₄ measurements. In Section 5, we present the RFC cloud clearing method, detailing its input and output parameters, as well as the training procedure for deriving the three RFC classifiers corresponding to cloud fractions of 0.1, 0.02, and 0.001. Section 6 assesses the performance of the RFC cloud clearing relative to VIIRS-based cloud clearing, validates TROPOMI CH₄ data against TCCON ground-based measurements using both filtering methods, and compares TROPOMI CH₄ data filtered with the RFC method to GOSAT-2 retrievals on a global scale. Section 7 offers concluding remarks on our findings.

2 List of abbreviations

Acronyms

ATBD Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document.

CO Carbon Monoxide.

ECMWF European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts.

ESA European Space Agency.

FTIR Fourier Transform Infrared.

GOSAT-2 Greenhouse Gases Observing Satellite-2.

KDE Kernel Density Estimation.

KNMI Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut.

NIR near-infrared.

NOAA-20 National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration-20.

OCO-2 Orbiting Carbon Observatory-2.

RemoTeC Remote Sensing of Greenhouse Gases for Carbon Cycle Modelling.

RFC Random Forest Classifier.

S5P Sentinel-5 Precursor.

SICOR Shortwave Infrared CO Retrieval.

SKLearn Scikit Learn.

SUOMI-NPP SUOMI-National Polar-orbiting Partnership.

SWIR short-wave infrared.

TCCON Total Carbon Column Observing Network.

TROPOMI Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument.

UMA Uniform Memory Access.

UV ultraviolet.

VIIRS Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite.

VIS visible.

VZA viewing zenith angle.

3 Relevant documents

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4 TROPOMI CH₄

The TROPOMI aboard European Space Agency (ESA)'s Sentinel-5 Precursor (S5P) satellite offers global coverage within a day and provides dry air mole fraction-averaged methane columns (XCH₄) for clear-sky scenes, boasting a spatial resolution of up to $5.5 \times 7 \text{ km}^2$. Utilizing a grating spectrometer with extensive spectral coverage spanning ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS), near-infrared (NIR), and short-wave infrared (SWIR) regions [Veefkind, 2012], the TROPOMI XCH₄ data product is derived from NIR and SWIR measurements employing the Remote Sensing of Greenhouse Gases for Carbon Cycle Modelling (RemoTeC) algorithm [Hu et al., 2018]. However, due to algorithmic constraints on viewing zenith angle (VZA), the swath width for TROPOMI XCH₄ is narrower, leading to limited daily global coverage.

Continuous enhancement efforts have been made in recent years to refine the TROPOMI XCH₄ product. Developments such as introducing a new bias correction scheme to mitigate XCH₄ dependence on scene brightness [Lorente et al., 2021], expanding dataset coverage to include observations over oceanic glint geometry [Lorente et al., 2022], and resolving XCH₄ anomalies over carbonated rock formations by refining surface reflectivity spectral fits [Lorente et al., 2023], exemplify these improvements. Widely utilized in detecting anthropogenic CH₄ emissions and atmospheric modeling [Lunt et al., 2019, Maasackers et al., 2022, Pandey et al., 2019], the TROPOMI XCH₄ dataset adheres to stringent mission requirements on precision (<1.5%) and accuracy (<1%), validated extensively against ground-based Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) measurements from the TCCON [Sha et al., 2021].

Ensuring such precision entails strict cloud clearing of TROPOMI measurements, given the potential for significant retrieval errors induced by clouds in the satellite's observation path. Despite lacking a dedicated cloud imager, S5P satellite's loose formation with the SUOMI-NPP satellite enables leveraging VIIRS cloud data for cloud clearing, thanks to synchronized ground scene capture within <3 minutes [Hu et al., 2016].

In this context, VIIRS data serves a dual purpose in ESA's data processing workflow. Initially employed for pre-filtering TROPOMI data to reduce processing volume—a preliminary step known as weak data filtering—the more demanding secondary step involves cloud clearing, where VIIRS data contribute to posteriori data filtering of retrieved XCH₄ data, ensuring data product integrity. In this study we discuss the cloud clearing of the TROPOMI CH₄ data product based on the cloud fraction = 0.02 (the current pre-filtering threshold) as well as based on the cloud fraction = 0.001 (post-filtering). In addition we also propose an updated pre-filtering to enhance global coverage based on a cloud fraction = 0.1, that will result in about 50% of more data.

In scenarios of missing VIIRS data there is already an alternative cloud filtering implemented for the TROPOMI CH₄ retrieval, that is based on threshold filtering. This filter incorporates information from weak and strong CH₄ absorption lines in the SWIR, available in the TROPOMI CO product output [Hu et al., 2016]. Similar approaches have been adopted for instruments like Orbiting Carbon Observatory-2 (OCO-2) [Taylor et al., 2016]. However, our investigation reveals the inadequacy of the backup filter, especially evident during SUOMI-NPP VIIRS instrument malfunction periods in August 2022 and November 2023. These incidents underscore the crucial role of VIIRS data in ensuring TROPOMI XCH₄ data quality, with observed biases and deviations in XCH₄ values during these periods [Borsdorff et al., 2024].

As SUOMI-NPP nears the end of its operational life, it will be succeeded by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration-20 (NOAA-20) satellite [Cao et al., 2018]. While NOAA-20 features a cloud imager akin to VIIRS, differing orbit positions result in a time gap of over 20 minutes with TROPOMI, posing challenges for critical cloud clearing of TROPOMI data. The dependence of TROPOMI XCH₄ data quality on VIIRS data product is evident from instances of VIIRS data unavailability and ensuing XCH₄ data biases, reinforcing the need for alternative cloud clearing strategies complementary to SUOMI-NPP measurements.

5 Algorithm Description

5.1 Optimized Random Forest Implementation

For operational purposes, the cloud filter developed in this study uses the Balsa Random Forest implementation. Balsa is a memory- and CPU-efficient C++ implementation of the Random Forest algorithm that was developed specifically for the TROPOMI cloud filter application. This section summarizes the general Random Forest algorithm, and it describes the internal data structures and techniques that were used in the Balsa implementation to achieve optimal performance. Detailed instruction on the installation and the source code can be found in the GitHub webpage (<https://github.com/borsdorff/Balsa>). In addition, the requirements for other relevant software/version are also listed.

5.1.1 Overview of the RF Algorithm

The Random Forest algorithm is an *ensemble classification* algorithm that uses a relatively large number of weaker classifiers to arrive at a stronger classification. In a Random Forest, the weaker classifiers are known as *decision trees*. During the training phase, incomplete decision trees with randomized mutations are trained on a set of known data points and labels. During classification, the data points of interest are labeled by each individual decision tree. The random forest selects the final label for each point by (weighted or un-weighted) majority voting.

Each decision tree consists of internal nodes and leaf nodes. Each leaf node represents a class label (e.g. 'cloudy' or 'clear sky'), and each internal node represents a decision of the form $p[k] < L$, where $p[k]$ is the k -th feature of data point p , and L is some constant limit. Note that both k and L can be different for each internal node. The tuple (k, L) is called a *split*. A point is classified by starting at the root of the tree. If the node is an internal node, its decision is evaluated. If the decision evaluates to 'true', the evaluation process continues at the left-most child node of the internal node. On the contrary, if it is 'false', evaluation continues to the right. If the process arrives at a leaf node, the label is applied to the point, and classification is finished.

Decision trees are created from a set of data points and known labels by a training process. At the start of the process, the tree contains only a single (leaf) node with a randomly chosen label. Conceptually, all points in the test set are contained in this leaf node. The process proceeds by finding a split that will separate the test points into two parts. This process is repeated for each leaf-node in the tree, until a stop criterion is reached. Common stop criteria for training decision trees are the *purity* of each node (in a 'pure' node all test points have the same label), the depth of the tree, the total number of nodes, or some combination thereof.

While any non-trivial split will eventually lead to a decision tree, it is important for overall size and performance to find an *optimal* split at each node. An optimal split is that choice of k and L that leads to the highest gain in *purity*. Purity can be measured using various information measures. Most RF implementations use Gini impurity, for its favorable combination of computational efficiency and effectiveness.

To achieve randomization of the forest, the training process selects a limited number of features to consider for each split. The number of features that will be scanned is a user selectable parameter. A typical default is to use the square root of the number of features.

5.1.2 Training Optimizations

A critical part of any RF trainer implementation is the speed and memory usage of the search process for the optimal split points of the tree nodes. In order to facilitate this process, Balsa starts by building a *feature index*. This index consists of a set of tables (one per feature) in which the IDs of all points in the test set are stored, sorted by feature value. In addition to the ID, the index also contains the label of the test point, for fast access. Each node in the decision tree contains a pointer to the range of the feature index that contains all the points that are part of that particular node. In addition, each node maintains counts of how many points of each label it contains.

At the start of training, the root node contains all points in the feature index. Because the sorting process is time-consuming, the feature index of an empty tree (a *sapling* containing only one root/leaf node) is computed only once for an entire random forest. The training process of each individual decision tree starts by deep-copying this sapling.

The feature index allows Balsa to sweep through all points in a leaf-node efficiently, one feature at a time. During the traversal, Balsa keeps a record of how many points of each label it has already seen during the sweep. Using the per-label totals in the leaf-node, it is then possible to compute the information gain that would be achieved if the split is made at that particular feature k and limit L .

When a split with optimal gain is found, new child nodes are created, and the relevant section of the feature index is partitioned into two parts. During the partitioning of the feature index, care is taken to not change the order of the entries, so no additional sorting is necessary.

5.1.3 Classification Optimization

The Balsa Random Forest classifier limits its peak memory usage and overall CPU performance by using a bulk-processing strategy. Balsa works most efficiently by classifying many points in one single pass. Unless Balsa is specifically configured to do otherwise, Balsa will only load as many trees into memory as there are worker threads. Consequently, the peak memory usage during classification is very low, compared to RF implementations that load the entire forest in advance. Another advantage is that model loading/disk access is done during classification.

Each individual decision tree model also utilizes bulk classification. The classifier starts by creating a list of point IDs (offsets into the input array of points). One internal node at a time, the classifier will partition this list of point IDs in-place according to the split criterion of the node ($p[k] < L$). When a leaf node is reached, the classifier casts its votes for the label of each point in the node. After each tree has cast its votes for each point in the batch, the votes are totalled to determine the final vote of the forest. As a result of the bulk-classification, the process of traversing the decision trees and finding the k, L values is amortized over traversal of the data points, leading to very low performance overhead.

5.1.4 Parallelization

Both the Balsa trainer and classifier are capable of utilizing multiple cores for speed gains. Both the training process and the classification process are trivial to perform in parallel, due to the fact that each tree is trained and used independently. On a Uniform Memory Access (UMA) system, Balsa performs the initial ‘sapling’ construction once for the entire forest. Worker threads use the sapling to initialize new trees that will be grown/developed randomly.

5.2 Cloud Clearing for TROPOMI CH₄

We trained the RFC algorithm on the co-located TROPOMI and VIIRS data. We specifically selected TROPOMI data with adequate cloud sensitivity and used only those input parameters that are available in the TROPOMI Carbon Monoxide (CO) product, which is processed prior to the TROPOMI CH₄ product. First, we utilized the CH₄ column data obtained from both weak and strong CH₄ absorption in the SWIR band, using a non-scattering radiative transfer model [Hu et al., 2016]. Differences between these columns highlight atmospheric scattering [Taylor et al., 2016]. The TROPOMI CO product, retrieved from TROPOMI SWIR observations, uses the Shortwave Infrared CO Retrieval (SICOR) algorithm [Landgraf et al., 2016] to infer total column density and effective cloud parameters. Cloud information is derived using prior knowledge of atmospheric CH₄ concentrations. The quality of CO data meets mission objectives [Borsdorff et al., 2018b, Borsdorff et al., 2018a, Borsdorff et al., 2020]. This data product includes the column averaging kernel [Borsdorff et al., 2014], which indicates vertical sensitivity to CO and the presence of clouds. The ground value of this kernel is particularly sensitive to cloud contamination, approaching approximately 0.9 under clear-sky conditions and gradually decreasing to 0 in the presence of clouds.

To summarise, we used the following key TROPOMI parameters:

1. the CH₄ column retrieved from a strong and weak CH₄ absorption feature in the SWIR spectrum,
2. the CO averaging kernel at the ground level,
3. the latitude of the observed ground scene,
4. the VZA of the observation,
5. the retrieved surface albedo at 2334 nm, and
6. European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) surface pressure

Please note that all the CO data used in this analysis are version 2.4.0 or later. The data retrieved from the SWIR measurements of TROPOMI show a significant artificial striping pattern in the flight direction of the satellite. These stripes are noticeable in the CO products and can be up-to a few percent in intensity. Most

Figure 1: Evaluation of the iterative training performance of the RFC, for the cloud fraction = 0.001 (left column), = 0.02 (middle column), and = 0.1 (right column), respectively. Within each columns, top panel (A) shows the relative number μ of true clear-sky and true-cloudy (red), false cloudy (yellow), and false clear-sky (blue) classifications as a function of the number of orbits used for training the RFC. These metrics are derived from the analysis of 1000 randomly selected orbits in each iteration. In the bottom panel (B), corresponding prediction scatter σ percentage is provided.

likely, these stripes are associated with the calibration of the TROPOMI level-0 data. Therefore, a posteriori double median smoothing destriping of the level-2 data has been implemented [Borsdorff et al., 2019] and we apply this destriping to all parameters. Afterwards, we implemented an iterative training approach of the RFC to optimize its performance. To ensure proper balance in the training set, we carefully matched the number of clear-sky and cloud-contaminated observations using the co-located VIIRS data. To this end, we first select all clear-sky retrievals and then randomly choose an equivalent number of cloudy data from the same orbit. Note that the large number of cloudy data allowed us to maintain this approach (e.g. typical orbit may yield approximately 20% clear-sky retrievals). Following the initial training, we evaluated the RFC’s performance on a test set comprising 1000 randomly selected orbits from a pool of approximately 20,000 available orbits. We identified the orbit with the highest number of false clear-sky predictions by the RFC, which we used subsequently to update the training set. Here, we ensure that the orbits in the training set are excluded in the test set.

False clear-sky classifications are the most detrimental, as they significantly reduce the accuracy of our data product. Accuracy here is defined as the relative number of true clear-sky classifications versus false cloudy classifications. In contrast, false cloudy classifications mainly impact data coverage by omitting true clear-sky measurements. To address this, our approach focuses on selecting orbits with the highest incidence of false clear-sky classifications to mitigate this specific error. This explanation applies to all cloud fraction thresholds analyzed, namely 0.001, 0.02, and 0.1.

Figure 1 illustrates the effectiveness of this methodology. Initially, training with only one orbit resulted in less than 60% accuracy and a false cloudy classification rate exceeding 40%, which led to a significant reduction in data coverage compared to the original cloud filtering based on resampled VIIRS data. As the number of orbits used for training increases, accuracy improves rapidly, with false cloudy classifications decreasing significantly. For all three cloud fraction thresholds (0.001, 0.02, and 0.1), accuracy rises to over 80%. However, this improvement can slightly increase false clear-sky measurements, although this increase remains $\sim 10\%$

for all cloud fractions. With more relaxed cloud fraction thresholds, false cloudy classifications improve as expected due to less stringent criteria. This behaviour is also observed in the scatter of predictions, which shows similar trends. The variability in scatter is largely driven by the false cloudy classifications, and this variability decreases as more orbits are included in the training set.

The final number of orbits used for training is crucial. It must be sufficient to reduce false cloudy classifications and associated scatter, while also keeping false clear-sky classifications to a minimum. Figure 1 shows that the optimal number of orbits typically falls between 100 and 150, balancing these performance metrics effectively.

6 Error analysis

6.1 Performance analysis

A C++ implementation of the Random Forest algorithm (prediction and training) has been developed. This implementation ('Balsa') has been validated against the Python-based SKLearn implementation, and against Ranger, a fast, third-party C++-based implementation. Notably, the Balsa implementation outperforms both Ranger and SKLearn in terms of wall clock time and memory usage, in both training and prediction. This development is particularly promising for the integration of the operational processor.

Figure 2: Memory consumption as function of dataset size for the RFC training phase (left panel) and the prediction phase (right panel). The Python-based SKLearn implementation (green), the C++ based C++ implementation Ranger (orange), and the newly developed C++ implementation Balsa are distinguished.

Figure 3: Total runtime as a function of dataset size for RFC training (left panel) and prediction (right panel). The Python-based SKLearn implementation (green), the C++ based C++ implementation Ranger (orange), and the newly developed C++ implementation Balsa are distinguished.

Figure 4: Plots of the prediction Accuracy (left) and True Positive Rate (right) as a function of training set size show that all three implementations have identical predictive performance, with minor variations due to the randomized nature of the algorithm.

Following an initial meeting with Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI), we developed an interface to ensure seamless integration of the C++ prediction component into the operational processor.

Concurrently, efforts to enhance the training of the RFCs for improved cloud filtering have commenced. Leveraging a dataset spanning six years of collocated TROPOMI and SUOMI-NPP data, we refined and optimized the cloud filtering process for enhanced accuracy and reliability.

6.2 Quality assessment

To evaluate the overall quality of the dataset using the RFC cloud filtering approach, we followed a comprehensive assessment process. We began by comparing our results with the current VIIRS filtering standard to gauge performance and accuracy. Next, we validated the RFC-filtered data using ground-based measurements from all 12 TCCON stations over the full 5-year period of the TROPOMI mission. Finally, we conducted an inter-comparison of the RFC-filtered TROPOMI data with measurements from the GOSAT-2 satellite. Details of these assessments are provided in the following subsections.

6.2.1 RFC comparison with VIIRS data

As an initial step in analysing the accuracy of our RFC cloud clearing method, it is essential to compare the results with those obtained using the VIIRS cloud filtering, which is the current standard method. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the performance of both cloud filtering approaches on the global CH₄ distribution. Please note that in this Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD), we present a comparison based on observations from a single day (September 13, 2023). For each cloud fraction (0.001, 0.02, and 0.1), we plotted the filtered data and presented a global comparison in Figure 5, with panels arranged from *top* to *bottom*, respectively. For each cloud fraction, the *left* panel displays the data filtered using VIIRS, while the *right* panel shows the data filtered using the RFC method.

Figure 5: Comparison of global maps of XCH₄ measurements for 13th September, 2023, filtered using VIIRS and RFC methods. Each column presents the daily global maps of XCH₄ coverage: the *left* panel displays data filtered with the VIIRS method, while the *right* panel shows data filtered with the RFC method. The cloud fractions used in these plots are 0.001, 0.02, and 0.1, arranged from *top* to *bottom* panels, respectively. As expected, with relaxed constraints on the cloud fraction, we retrieve a significant amount of more data, improving the global coverage by 50%.

Firstly, we notice that the global maps of the VIIRS and RFC filtering agree well and they are consistent with the varying cloud fractions. Secondly, in all cases, the glint measurements are very well preserved. And

finally, we notice that with the relaxed constraints on the cloud fraction, we retrieve a significant amount of more data, improving the global coverage by 50%. Furthermore, for a given cloud fraction, our RFC method filters out more data points compared to VIIRS filtering. We suspect this is because the RFC method uses real-time, co-located CO data, whereas VIIRS filtering involves a delay of a few minutes relative to TROPOMI. This real-time capability likely enhances the RFC method's performance in cloud filtering, particularly for pixels with lower XCH₄ measurements.

Figure 6: Histogram distributions of cf of daily global maps of XCH₄ coverage (date: 13th September, 2023) for VIIRS (*left* panel) and RFC (*right* panel), respectively. The cloud fraction used in these plots are 0.001, 0.02, and 0.1 respectively, from *top* to *bottom* panels. These values are also noted in the sub-figures with **CF** = 0.001, 0.02 and 0.1.

In addition to comparing global maps, we calculated statistics for both the RFC and VIIRS methods as part of the validation process. We evaluated the mean, median, and standard deviations of the data from these global maps and compared the results between RFC cloud clearing and VIIRS filtering. Figure 6 shows the histogram distributions of the pixels for each method. In the figure, mean, median, and standard deviation values are represented by *blue*, *red*, and *green* dotted lines, respectively. Each row in the figure corresponds to a different cloud fractions (e.g.: 0.001, 0.02, and 0.1 with panels arranged from *top* to *bottom*), with the left column displaying VIIRS filtering and the right column showing RFC filtering. We found that the mean, median, and standard deviation values are almost identical for each cloud fraction and are in good agreement between the two methods. This consistency is maintained across varying cloud fractions. Moreover, the distribution shapes are preserved, with the two distinct peaks clearly visible. These similarities reflect the close agreement between the two methods.

6.2.2 Validation with TCCON

The quality of the operational TROPOMI XCH₄ data is subjected to validation and continuous monitoring using XCH₄ reference data from the TCCON [Hasekamp et al., 2021] stations. To assess the effectiveness of the RFC cloud clearing approach, we processed five years of TROPOMI data around 12 TCCON sites (within a radius of 300 km), where we intentionally refrained from applying any cloud screening. This approach allows us to make a direct comparison between the different cloud clearing techniques using collocated VIIRS data and the RFC method.

Figure 7: Validation Statistics for TROPOMI XCH₄ daily means at 12 TCCON Stations (2018 to 2022). The *left* panel (quoted as **RFC**) shows cloud clearing using the RFC method, and the *right* panel (quoted as **VIIRS**) shows filtering using the VIIRS method, respectively. In each case, the top panel displays the mean bias (TROPOMI - TCCON) for each TCCON station, calculated from the daily means. The lower panel shows the standard deviation of the mean bias. $\bar{b}$ represents the average bias across all stations, and $\sigma(\bar{b})$ is the corresponding standard deviation. $\bar{\sigma}$ denotes the average standard deviation across all station standard deviations, and $\sigma(\bar{\sigma})$ is the standard deviation of the mean standard deviations. The *bottom* panels, show the number of counts per stations, that are used to calculate the statistics.

For each station, we derived XCH₄ time series of daily means for both TCCON and TROPOMI. By using these daily means, we calculate the validation statistics, that is shown in Figure 7. In this figure, we show the comparison of the results from our RFC filtering approach (*left* panel) and VIIRS filtering (*right* panel), with cloud fraction = 0.001. In the top panel, $\bar{b}$ represents the average bias across all stations, and $\sigma(\bar{b})$ is the corresponding standard deviation of the mean bias. In the middle panel, $\bar{\sigma}$ denotes the average standard deviation across all station standard deviations, and $\sigma(\bar{\sigma})$ is the standard deviation of the mean standard deviations. In the *bottom* panels, we show the number of counts per stations, that are used to calculate the above-mentioned statistics. Overall, we see very good agreement in the bias (-8.5 ppb for RFC vs -5.6 ppb for

Figure 8: Validation Statistics for TROPOMI XCH₄ daily means at 12 TCCON Stations (2018 to 2022) using the RFC cloud clearing approach; for cloud fraction = 0.02 (*left panel*), and cloud fraction = 0.1 (*right panel*), respectively. The details of the statistical parameters, are the same as in Figure 7. As expected, with more relaxed constraints on the cloud fraction, the parameters have a higher mean and standard deviation, when compared to case for cloud fraction = 0.001. However, even with the relaxed constraints, the values align reasonably well with the TCCON measurement provide reliable estimates on the XCH₄ retrievals.

VIIRS) and in the standard deviation of the bias (13.7 ppb for RFC vs 12 ppb for VIIRS).

We also calculated the same statistical parameters for the other two cloud fractions of 0.02 and 0.1 using the RFC approach, and the comparison is shown in Figure 8. As we can see, as the constraints for the cloud fraction are relaxed, the amount of data increases (bottom panels in Figure 8). We measure the mean biases to be $\bar{b} = -13.4$ ppb and -15.5 ppb, and their standard deviations $\bar{\sigma} = -16.8$ ppb and -19.5 ppb respectively, for cloud fractions = 0.02 and 0.1. These values indicate that even with the relaxed constraints on the cloud fraction, the values are very comparable and in good agreement with TCCON measurements. It is important to note that the deterioration of these measurements, compared to a cloud fraction of 0.001, is expected. This trend indicates that as the dataset grows larger with more relaxed cloud fraction constraints, the agreement with TCCON measurements slightly worsens. The anticipated increase in mean bias and standard deviation occurs because adding more data points, particularly those with higher cloud fractions, likely introduces greater variability and potential noise. However, despite this slight worsening, the values remain relatively close, indicating that even with relaxed constraints (cloud fractions of 0.02 and 0.1), the measurements still align reasonably well with the TCCON measurements. This suggests that the user can select the data based on their requirements and keep a balance between expanding the dataset size and maintaining data quality, acknowledging that a cloud fraction constraint of 0.001 might offer the best agreement but significantly reduces the available data.

6.2.3 Inter-comparison with GOSAT-2

Comparing XCH₄ measurements, retrieved from different satellites serve as a reliable benchmark and therefore is a crucial step to prove the accuracy for our RFC cloud clearing approach. Despite the different spectral ranges and retrieval methods used for these satellites, previous studies [Haili et al., 2018, Lorente et al., 2023] have demonstrated that GOSAT measurements can be used for such comparisons. Additionally, inter-satellite comparisons are essential for evaluating glint measurements, as this data cannot be obtained from ground-based stations. In this subsection, we compared our results with the XCH₄ product obtained from the GOSAT-2 satellite.

First, we present the global map comparison from both satellites in Figure 9. This figure displays the global distribution of XCH₄ on a latitude/longitude grid with 2x2 degree boxes, averaged over one day of observation (13 September, 2023), for both GOSAT-2 (*left column*) and TROPOMI (*right column*). Each row represents a

Figure 9: Global XCH₄ distribution obtained from GOSAT-2 (*left* column) and TROPOMI (*right* column) measurements for one day (13th September, 2023), with a QA value of 0 for the GOSAT-2 Full Physics product. The cloud fractions used are 0.001, 0.02, and 0.1, shown from *top* to *bottom* panels. Both panels display maps of XCH₄ daily averages collocated and sampled in 2° × 2° boxes.

Figure 10: Correlation between all collocated XCH₄ measurements, shown as a KDE plot. The mean bias, standard deviation, number of points and correlation coefficient of the population are also quoted. Histograms of the number of counts are shown around the margins, along with the linear regression and the 1-to-1 lines in black and grey respectively.

different cloud fraction used in the document, that are 0.001, 0.02, and 0.1. For all the cloud fractions, both datasets reveal expected features, including the latitudinal gradient and regional enhancements in American continent, Africa and Asia, associated with human activities such as biomass burning and agriculture. In addition, very clearly, we can spot the glint measurements from both the satellites. As anticipated, with more relaxed constraints on the cloud fraction, we are retrieving more data and increasing the global coverage.

We also calculated the statistics for the differences in measurements between these two satellites. The bias between TROPOMI and GOSAT-2 was calculated by averaging XCH₄ onto 2x2 degree grid boxes for one day (September 13, 2023) and then determining the difference where data from both satellites were available. In Figure 10, we have shown the correlation between all collocated XCH₄ measurements as a KDE plot. We have also plotted the histograms of the number of counts around the margins, along with the linear regression and the 1-to-1 lines in black and grey, respectively. We find the mean of the differences, that is the bias, is 5.61 ppb and the standard deviation is 14.16 ppb. We find that the Pearson's correlation coefficient is 0.89, indicating a high correlation among the data points. Even though, the data points are limited due to the single day of observation, we can see that the two datasets are in excellent agreement, with low average global biases, and high correlation coefficients, and standard deviations less than 1% of XCH₄.

7 Conclusion

We presented a theoretical baseline for a new cloud clearing approach in the TROPOMI XCH₄ data product, which employs a cloud filter based on the Balsa Random Forest implementation. Balsa is a C++-based, memory- and CPU-efficient version of the Random Forest algorithm, designed specifically for optimizing cloud filtering in TROPOMI product. The integrity of the TROPOMI XCH₄ data hinges on precise cloud clearing of spectrometer data, a process historically facilitated by the SUOMI-NPP VIIRS cloud product. Over the past six years of mission operation, this method has proven highly effective, benefiting from both satellites operating in close formation, ensuring synchronized ground scene capture with minimal delay of 2–3 minutes. However, the forthcoming decommissioning of SUOMI-NPP necessitates the development of an alternative cloud-clearing mechanism for the TROPOMI XCH₄ data product. This urgency stems from the significant time gap of approximately 20 minutes between TROPOMI and the NOAA-20 satellite, SUOMI-NPP's successor, compounded by the malfunctioning backup cloud filter in the current TROPOMI XCH₄ processor. To uphold the accuracy and reliability of the TROPOMI XCH₄ data, a novel cloud-clearing methodology was imperative in response to this evolving scenario.

In this document we explained a novel machine learning approach based on a random forest classifier technique, mirroring VIIRS cloud clearing exclusively using TROPOMI data in detail. The classifier underwent training utilizing a subset of 5 years of co-located TROPOMI and SUOMI-NPP VIIRS data, comprising approximately 20,000 orbits. Leveraging parameters derived from the TROPOMI CO retrieval, inherently sensitive to cloud presence and processed prior to TROPOMI XCH₄ retrieval, facilitated seamless integration into the existing processing framework. This study examines the cloud clearing of the TROPOMI CH₄ data product using three cloud fraction thresholds: 0.02 for pre-filtering, 0.001 for post-filtering, and a proposed new pre-filtering threshold of 0.1. The updated threshold aims to enhance global coverage and is expected to increase the available data by approximately 50%. We applied these thresholds to predict cloud contamination and filtered the TROPOMI XCH₄ product accordingly.

To assess the performance and accuracy of the new RFC implementation, we first compared our results with the current standard of VIIRS filtering. The results showed close agreement, accommodating more data and effectively handling challenging cloud contamination cases, especially at lower XCH₄ values. Moreover, the distributions from both methods exhibited similar behaviour, with closely aligned mean, median, and standard deviation values. Subsequently, we validated the RFC filtering results using TCCON data from all 12 stations over the complete 5-year period of the TROPOMI mission. Our analysis demonstrated excellent agreement in both bias and standard deviation when compared to TCCON data. The similarity in bias between TROPOMI and TCCON measurements for both VIIRS and RFC filtering techniques underscores the effectiveness of our RFC cloud clearing approach across all examined cloud fractions. Finally, we conducted an inter-comparison of RFC-filtered TROPOMI data with GOSAT-2 satellite data. The global comparison between these two satellites highlighted expected features and effectively captured glint geometries. Additionally, statistical analysis of the collocated data demonstrated excellent agreement between the datasets, characterized by low average global biases, high correlation coefficients, and standard deviations of less than 1% for XCH₄.

In the future, we plan to leverage this new library for further enhancements to the TROPOMI CH₄ data products. Our method shows significant potential for advancements such as integrating AI-based quality filtering with RFC classifiers. This approach will also be a crucial component in developing a Near-Real-Time TROPOMI CH₄ data product.